

TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF THE COLLEGE FACULTY AND DIGITAL LIBRARY SERVICES: IMPLICATION ON THE UTILIZATION OF SUCH SERVICES FOR INSTRUCTIONAL ACTIVITIES

Grace C. Vidal and Annabelle P. Acedera

Lourdes College - Graduate Studies, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The integration of technological competence and digital library services is deemed essential for enhancing teaching-learning environments. This study aimed to determine the influence of digital library services and technological competence on college faculty's utilization of digital services to instructional activities. This study investigated the implications of technological competence of college faculty and their assessment of digital library services utilized for instructional activities. A descriptive-correlational research design, a method renowned for its ability to unravel the intricate relationships among variables. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression were used to generate the findings of the study. The utilization of web-based library services influences the college faculty's instructional activities. It confirms the Interaction Triptych Framework that technological competence and engagement can directly impact the faculty's instructional activities. It is inferred that technologically competent faculty members are more likely to effectively utilize technology to create engaging and effective learning experiences for their students. The study suggests that web-based library services impact college faculty's instructional activities, requiring a deep understanding of technology, content, and user interactions in digital environments to determine the effectiveness of their instructional methodologies.

Keywords: *technological competence, college faculty, digital library services, instructional activities*

INTRODUCTION

Technological competence and digital library services are crucial in the digitized academic world, significantly impacting college faculty instructional activities. Information access is being revolutionized by technology, and educators must properly

incorporate digital resources and assess their effects on teaching-learning environments.

As noted by Durak (2021), educators are expected to incorporate emergent digital technology into their instruction; yet, just because they are adept with technology does not guarantee that they can use it effectively for teaching (Christensen & Knezek, 2017). Digital competence, in addition to pedagogical context knowledge, is a prerequisite for teaching in the digital age, as emphasized by Artacho et al. (2020) and Phan et al. (2020). To teach in a technology-enabled learning network in the modern day, educators must be technically proficient and digitally literate.

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, technological competence is a necessity, particularly in education. For college faculty, the ability to effectively incorporate digital resources into their instructional services is becoming increasingly crucial in order to meet the diverse learning needs and preferences of students. Digital libraries provide college faculty with extensive resources to enhance teaching methods, engage students, and create interactive learning environments. Brevik et al. (2019) argue that for educators to successfully employ and integrate technology into their teaching methods, they must be digitally competent and have the necessary knowledge, abilities, and competence.

In contrast, despite the evident importance of technological competence and the growing availability of digital services and resources, there is a noticeable gap in the literature, particularly in Northern Mindanao. Despite the growing emphasis on digitization within educational institutions, research on digitization in educational institutions often overlooks the unique challenges and opportunities faced by college faculty in effectively using digital library services and enhancing technological competence to enrich instruction.

Subsequently, while international research studies have examined the implications of technological competence and digital library services in education at large, there is a dearth of research exploring the impact on college faculty instructional services within a state university in the region. By addressing this gap, scholars and educators can gain valuable insights that are tailored to the specific educational landscape of said region.

Thus, this study aims to offer localized insights into faculty needs and challenges in integrating digital resources, thereby guiding the design of discipline-specific interventions and initiatives, thereby contributing to existing literature.

Theoretical Framework

This study assumes that technological competence and digital library services substantiated by the Interaction Triptych Framework, developed by Giannis Tsakonas and Christos Papatheodorou in 2006.

The Interaction Triptych Framework (ITF), as illustrated in Figure 1, serves as a foundational model in understanding the interplay between user, system, and content in the context of *technological competence*. At the heart of this framework lies

the principle of integrated interaction among these three core elements. The *user*, as one of the core elements in this study, refers to the college faculty of a state university in Northern Mindanao. These users interact with the technology. This interaction refers to the second core element called as *system*. Meanwhile, their technological competence and engagement with digital library services are part of the *content*, the third core element. This third component is pivotal, as this can directly impact the faculty's instructional activities. The college faculty's technological competence plays a significant role in determining the success of the technology-enhanced learning environment. Faculty members who are more technologically competent are more likely to effectively use the technology to create engaging and effective learning experiences for their students.

According to The Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education (SITE), today's teachers must be technology literate to teach the new generation of students. The UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers, 2018) identifies unique competencies needed by instructors to become skillful in using technological tools. These competencies are set of technology standards that define teacher proficiency in using computer technology in the classroom. These computer-related skills are grouped into four related domains such as: *basic technology operations*; *professional use of technology tools*; *social, ethical and privacy issues*; and *application of technology in instruction*. These domains are discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

In the specific context of this study, the college faculty, as end users, interact with the digital library system to access various digital services. This interaction is critical in determining how effectively the digital library services facilitate and enhance the college faculty's instructional methodologies. Through the lens of the ITF, this study aims to dissect and understand the nuances of these interactions and their impact on educational outcomes in a state university setting.

The influence of digital library services on college faculty's instructional activities can be profoundly understood by exploring into the nuances of content, technology, and user interactions within these digital environments. The Information Technology Foundation (ITF) plays a pivotal role in providing insights into these dynamics, particularly through a comprehensive evaluation based on three critical interaction axes: *usability*, *usefulness*, and *performance*, as delineated by Fuhr et al. (2007), Heradio et al. (2012), and Tsakonas et al. (2004).

The Information Technology Foundation (ITF) offers a strong and systematic framework for assessing digital library services, intricately considering the dynamic interplay between users, the system, and its content. This study employs this framework to meticulously evaluate digital library services across three pivotal dimensions: usability, usefulness, and performance. Such a comprehensive approach is instrumental in discerning the extent to which these services impact and shape college faculty's instructional activities.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a descriptive-correlational research design, a method renowned for its ability to unravel the intricate relationships among variables. Stangor and Walinga (2019) argue that this design combines descriptive observation with the characteristic of correlational analysis. This design is deemed appropriate as the present study aimed to determine the influence of digital library services on college faculty's instructional activities.

The study was participated by 270 college faculty members from different colleges or department of a state university in Northern Mindanao. These participants are working full-time during the second semester of the academic year 2023–2024. Using random sampling, also known as probability sampling, is a sampling technique that enables the randomization of sample selection (Creswell, 2015) the participants were randomly selected from the different departments of the universities involved in this study.

In this study, the research instruments were based on the established and validated questionnaires developed by Eligan (2022), Galagal (2018), Ladera (2018), and Platino (2022). These instruments were strategically divided into three parts, each targeting a unique aspect of digital library services and their integration into faculty activities in a higher education setting. Part I of the instrument was designed to investigate the extent of College faculty assessment of digital library services. Part II of the questionnaire was focused on the level of participants' technological competence in terms of basic technology operations; professional use of technology; ethical, legal and privacy issues; and application of technology in instruction. Part III aimed to understand how these digital library services are being applied in the instructional activities by the college faculty.

Prior to the commencement of data collection, the research instrument underwent a rigorous process of validation and reliability assessment. For the validity of the instrument, questions were reviewed by a panel of 3 to 5 experts in the relevant field. The reviews made by both panel members and experts in the field provided critical feedbacks and suggestions to the extent to which an instrument measures what it was intended to measure. The researcher underwent a series of methodical steps to ensure that the study was conducted ethically and efficiently. Initially, obtaining approval from the Lourdes College Research and Ethics Committee was the primary step of this research undertaking. This is a crucial process to guarantee that the study adheres to the necessary ethical standards and procedures. Once approval was secured from the said committee, the next step involved the asking of permission from the Chancellor to conduct the research within the campus of the state university.

Following the Chancellor's approval, the researcher approached the Deans of various colleges to gain authorization to administer the questionnaire to the teachers in their respective classrooms. The questionnaire, designed to be completed by college faculty in their respective workplaces, clearly stated the purpose of the study and provided comprehensive instructions to minimize any potential confusion. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to each participant based on the agreed time at their respective workplaces. Each participant was given 30 minutes to

respond to the questionnaire. Upon completion, researcher collected back the research instrument. The data obtained from the responses of the participants were then collated, organized, tabulated and statistically treated for analysis and interpretation.

In this study, different statistical methods were used to analyze the data for various research problems. For the first three problems, the study used descriptive statistical tools. For the fourth problem, multiple regression analysis was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. What is the participants' assessment of digital library services in terms of: usability; usefulness; and performance?

Table 1 presents the summary table of the participants assessment of digital library services. The data revealed that the participants rated the digital library services as "high" as revealed in the overall mean of 4.05. From the specific dimensions, both usability and usefulness were having a "high" rating of the participants' assessment as indicated in the overall mean rating of 4.06. Though lowest among the mean rating (4.04), the assessment of the participants for performance is still generally "high."

Table 1

Summary Table of Assessment of Digital Library Services

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Usability	4.06	High	0.88
Usefulness	4.06	High	0.91
Performance	4.04	High	0.92
Overall	4.05	High	0.88

Problem 2. What is the level of participants' technological competence?

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' level of technological competence. The overall mean of 4.09 reveals that the participants have a "high" level of technological competence. Based on the results, 47.53% of the participants have a "high" level of technological competence, while 33.95% of them have a "very high" level. Meanwhile, 14.20 of them are on a "moderate level."

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Level of Technological Competence

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	55	33.95
3.51-4.50	High	77	47.53
2.51-3.50	Moderate	23	14.20
1.51-2.50	Low	6	3.70

1.00-1.50	Very Low	1	0.62
Total		162	100.0
Overall Mean		4.09	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.79	

Problem 3. What is the extent of the participants' utilization of the digital library services considering the following: course preparation; syllabi construction; lesson planning; and test development?

Table 3 presents the summary table of the participants' utilization of digital library services. As a whole, the participants' utilization of the digital library services are "high" as revealed in the overall mean rating of 3.75.

Specifically, highest among the participants' rating of the digital library services are on lesson planning (3.83), followed by syllabus construction and test development that got both the mean score of 3.77. Although, course preparation is lowest among the dimensions of digital library services, the overall mean rating of 3.64 is still interpreted as "high"

Table 3

Summary Table of Utilization of Digital Library Services

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Course Preparation	3.64	High	0.98
Syllabus Construction	3.77	High	0.95
Lesson Planning	3.83	High	1.03
Test Development	3.77	High	1.03
Overall	3.75	High	0.96

Problem 4. Do the participants' assessment of the digital library services and their technological competence significantly influence utilization of digital library services to instructional activities?

Table 4 presents the regression analysis of the influence of participants' assessment of the digital library services and their technological competence on their utilization of digital library services. Data reveal that the whole model is significant ($F = 77.11, p = .000$). This implies that participants who gave high ratings to the digital library services and their utilization of these services are likely having high technological competence.

Table 4

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants' Assessment of the Digital Library Services and their Technological Competence on their Utilization of Digital Library Services

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t
(Constant)	.244	.297		.821
				Sig.
				.413

Assessment of Digital Library Service	.538	.082	.496	6.57**	.000
Technological Competence	.324	.092	.266	3.53**	.001

Model Summary

R = .702 R² = .493 Adjusted R² = .487 F = 77.77** p = .000

**significant at 0.01 level

As to the specific variables, their assessment of digital library service came out as having the highest influence on the outcome variable indicating that for every unit increase in their assessment of this service, there is a corresponding .538 increase in their utilization of such service (B=.538, t=6.57, p = .000).

Furthermore, 49.3 percent of the variability in their utilization of digital library services can be accounted for by a combination of their assessment of the digital library services and their technological competence. The remaining 50.7 percent of the study's findings can be attributed to factors beyond the scope of the study, such as library awareness and access location. Further, challenges faced regarding access and utilization of digital information services in the library, such as scarce finance, technological skills, and people, can also affect the utilization of digital library services.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study aims to evaluate the technological competence of digital library services in enhancing the instructional activities of college faculty at a state university. The study uses the Information Technology Foundation's framework to evaluate digital library services. Based on the findings, it may be implied that utilization of web-based library services influences the college faculty's instructional activities. This finding confirms the Interaction Triptych Framework that technological competence and engagement can directly impact the faculty's instructional activities. It is inferred that technologically competent faculty members are more likely to effectively utilize technology to create engaging and effective learning experiences for their students.

The college faculty in this particular study interact with the digital library system as end users to access a range of digital services. The interaction between faculty and digital library services is crucial for determining the effectiveness of their instructional methodologies. A solid understanding, therefore, of the technology, content, and user interactions present in these digital environments is imperative to comprehend how college faculty members' instructional activities are influenced by digital library services. Librarians may strengthen their engagement with faculty members and school officials to foster stronger relationships and ensure full support for library activities. Librarians may strengthen their engagement with faculty members and school officials to foster stronger relationships and ensure full support for library activities. Also, Librarians may identify the specific needs of college faculty, tailored to their teaching and learning requirements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To respect participant autonomy, faculty member can choose to skip any questions they do not wish to answer and proceed to the next one. The researcher will that the participants' consent to participate in the study is secure and safe. Furthermore, the participants will be assured that all their comments will be kept confidential. All information they provide will be recognized and presented accurately.

The researcher emphasizes that participation in the research study is entirely voluntary and participants have the clear right to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. The decision of the participate or withdraw will not be impact any existing relationships or commitments. This assurance is particularly important given the nature of the study involving librarians and faculty, as it underscores respect for individual confidentiality. This measure ensures that participants maintain control over their contributions, fostering a sense of comfort and trust in the research process. The overarching goal is to uphold ethical standards, promote transparency, and create positive research environment for the participants.

The research findings will be made accessible to the people who will the most from this study just like educators and future researchers. Likewise, results of this study may be shared to publications and conferences.

REFERENCES

- Artacho, E. G., Martinez, T. S., Martin, J. L. O., Marin, J. A. M., & Gomez, G. G. (2020). Teacher training in lifelong learning-the importance of digital competence in the encouragement of teaching innovation. *Sustainability*, 12, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072852>
- Brevik, L. M., Guomundsdottir, G. B., Lund, A., & Stromme, T. A. (2019). Transformative agency in teacher education: Fostering professional digital competence. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 86(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18146627.2015.1110912>
- Christensen, R., & Knezek, G. (2017). Validating the technology proficiency self-assessment questionnaire for 21st century learning (TPSA C-21). *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 33(1), 20-31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2016.1242391>
- Durak, Hatice (2021) Modeling of relations between K-12 teachers' TPACK levels and their technology integration self-efficacy, technology literacy levels, attitudes toward technology and usage objectives of social networks. DOI:10.1080/10494820.2019.1619591.
- Eligan, Eileen Andrea Mae. (2023). Influence of Library Marketing Strategies on the Utilization of Library Resources and Services in State Universities and Colleges in Region VI, Philippines. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Applied Sciences*.
- Fuhr, N., et al. (2007). Evaluation of digital libraries. *International Journal of Digital Libraries*, 8, 21-38.

- Heradio, R., et al. (2012). A review of quality evaluation of digital libraries based on users' perceptions. *Journal of Information Science*, 38(3), 269-283.
- Ladera, L.T. (2018). Usefulness and usability of subscribed online databases : predictors of stakeholders' research productivity [Unpublished master's thesis]. Lourdes College, Cagayan de Oro City.
- Phan, T. C., Ngo, T. T., & Phan, T. M. (2020). Assessment of information technology use competence for teachers: Identifying and applying the information technology competence framework in online teaching. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 12(1), 149-162.
<https://doi.org/10.30880/jtet.2020.12.01.016>
- Platino, E.C. (2022). Assessment and utilization of digital library services in the new normal: implications to students' academic application [Unpublished master's thesis]. Lourdes College, Cagayan de Oro City.
- Stangor, C., & Walinga, J. (2019). 3.5 psychologists use descriptive, correlational, and experimental research designs to understand behaviour. *Introduction to Psychology*.
- The Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education (2018). today's teachers must be technology literate to teach the new generation of students. The UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers.
- Tsakonas, G., & Papatheodorou, C. (2006). Analysing and evaluating usefulness and usability in electronic information services. *Journal of Information Science*, 32(5), 400–419.
- Tsakonas & Papatheodorou (2006) Library resources, with their vast collections of e-books, databases, and multimedia tools.
- Tsakonas, G., Kapidakis, S., & Papatheodorou, C. (2004). Evaluation of user interaction in digital libraries. Retrieved from http://dlib.ionio.gr/wp7/workshop2004_program.html
- UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers. (2018). The Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education.